

Storm-surge simulations: a quantitative comparison of some open-source shallow-water solvers

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Abstract

Storm-surge simulations contribute key information to decisions with huge geographical coverage, future projection and socio-economical relevance. Available analytical solutions provide partial but exact benchmarks for unsteady wind-driven flows. These can be used as one means to verify the quality of numerical simulations of storm surges. This avenue is undertaken here with application to three open-source flow solvers for the shallow-water equations: AdCirc, D-Flow Flexible Mesh, and Telemac. This extended summary outlines the assumptions, potentialities and outcomes of verification exercises addressing storm-surge modelling skills.

1 Context and relevance

Storm surges and meteo-tsunamis are threats to coastal areas possibly resulting in flooding and loss of property and life. A commonly-adopted metric for decisions and interventions concerning the vulnerability of flood-prone areas is risk, regarded as the product of hazard and damage. Since computer simulations are instrumental to quantifying both hazards and impacts of flood-bearing events, errors on the part of a flow solver imply some error in the risk appraisal. Yet, each flow solver delivers its own approximation of the statements of mass and momentum conservation in view of the chosen mathematical formulation, parametrisation of physical processes, solving algorithms and software coding.

This investigation promotes a unified and objective assessment of the skills that flow solvers have at simulating storm surges. The starting point are the exact benchmarks for unsteady wind-driven flows proposed by Sobey (2002).

2 Benchmarks for storm surge simulations

No single verification tests is sufficient, but any is necessary Sobey (2002) gives two analytical solutions of the linearised shallow-water equations regarding the surge development in a partially-open rectangular basins with uniform depth — a crude yet relevant schematisation for harbours as well as for shelf seas. These solutions describe the flow patterns driven by a uniform wind suddenly applied to the whole basin, and by a wind pulse travelling over it — these are schematisations for synoptic-scale weather systems and for squall lines.

The analytical description of the surge flow has rapid changes in sign and in rates of change, for both water levels and velocities. This complexity is adequate for putting to the test a solver's skills at following the temporal development of forces and motion, the excluded non-linearities (advection, quadratic friction) nonetheless. Rather, the simplification of linearisation helps identify problematic areas and triage sources of error in isolation — no single verification tests is sufficient, but any is necessary.

The feasibility and purpose of benchmarking using both Sobey's test cases has already been proven by Lipari (2015). This short account draws from the case with forcing by a sudden uniform wind. Extended results, also for the forcing by a wind pulse, are presented at the symposium.

Simplified but exact solutions for storm-surge situations The linearised equations for the mass and x -momentum conservation in a water column of height H are:

$$\frac{\partial \eta}{\partial t} = -H \frac{\partial u}{\partial x} \qquad \frac{\partial u}{\partial t} = -g \frac{\partial \eta}{\partial x} - \lambda u + \frac{\mathcal{F}_0}{H} \quad (1)$$

where η the free-surface elevation with respect to H , u is the depth-averaged velocity, λ the coefficient for a linear parametrisation of bed friction, $\mathcal{F}_0 = \tau_s/\rho_w$ the wind forcing term combining the surface shear stress τ_s and the water density ρ_w . The motion driven by a sudden, uniform, onshore wind applied over a partially-open basin starting from rest and with unchanging water depth at the open boundary is described by

$$\eta(x,t) = \frac{\mathcal{F}_0}{gH}x + e^{-\frac{\lambda}{2}t} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \left(\cos \omega_n t + \frac{\lambda}{2} \frac{\sin \omega_n t}{\omega_n} \right) \hat{f}_n X_n(x) \quad u(x,t) = e^{-\frac{\lambda}{2}t} \frac{1}{H} \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{\sin \omega_n t}{\omega_n} \hat{g}_n Y_n(x) \quad (2)$$

For each oscillating mode n , the space-dependent coefficients and functions are determined from the basin length L with

$$\beta_n = \left(n - \frac{1}{2} \right) \frac{\pi}{L} \quad X_n = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \sin \beta_n x \quad Y_n = \sqrt{\frac{2}{L}} \cos \beta_n x \quad \hat{f}_n = -\frac{\mathcal{F}_0}{gH} \int_0^L x X_n(x) dx \quad \hat{g}_n = \mathcal{F}_0 \int_0^L Y_n(x) dx \quad (3)$$

whence the angular velocities ω_n follow from the long-wave dispersion relationship

$$\omega_n = \sqrt{gH\beta_n^2 - \lambda^2/4} \quad (4)$$

Equations (2)–(4) predict a motion in which the steady-state setting (tilted free surface and even mass exchange at the boundary) is reached after a transient of damped oscillations travelling between the ends of the basin with alternating mass exchange at the open boundary. This already indicates that the maximum surge occurs earlier than the establishment of the steady state. As an example, Figure 1 illustrates the temporal development of the exact depth-averaged velocity at different stations in the basin. The parameters applied are $H = 2$ m, $L = 5000$ m, $\tau_s = 1.5$ N/m² (roughly corresponding to a wind speed of 25 m/s), and the pair $\lambda = 0$ and $1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s⁻¹.

Figure 1: Exact time histories of depth-averaged velocity from Equation (2) — Left: frictionless basin, $\lambda = 0$. Right: with bed friction, $\lambda = 1 \cdot 10^{-4}$ s⁻¹ — Locations and line labels: open boundary (0); one quarter (1), one half (2), three quarters (3) of the basin length; downwind end (4).

The open-source flow solvers compared here are AdCirc (version 52.30.13), D-Flow FM (1.1.116), Telemac (7.0.1). Briefly, these solvers may differ for the mathematical formulation of the conservation statements (primitive equations or elaborations thereof), for the space discretisation method (finite elements or finite volumes), for the schemes for temporal and spatial integration, and for the iterative methods to invert systems of algebraic equations. Additionally, each solver has settings for toggling and tuning specific features and for optimizing its performance or suitability to special cases.

Here, these solvers have been set to solve the equations (1) by skipping the calculation of advective terms, diffusive terms and Coriolis force, by selecting a linear law for bottom friction, by prescribing a wind field, a fixed elevation as open-boundary condition (hence, letting the water to flow freely through it) and, finally, consistent initial conditions. This tuning consists in editing keywords in a master input file and in providing data files as specified in the user's manuals (Luettich and Westerink, 2016; Hervouet and Ata, 2014; Deltares, 2015). A time step of 5 s, a simulated time of 6 h (as in Figure 1) and semi-implicit time-integration algorithms have been chosen. The basin has been discretised with one unstructured mesh of triangles having edges of 25 m. Other solver-specific parameters have been chosen so as to provide maximum accuracy, possibly modifying default settings.

Performance assessments for flow solvers The exact motion field in equations (2)-(4) enables to probe requirements and sensitivities of the numerical solution. For example, the comparison for a frictionless basin ($\lambda = 0$) shown in Figure 2

checks for spurious dissipation, since the exact motion is periodic (Figure 1 left) and this feature should be reproduced by any numerical solver tuned to handle the parent equations (1). AdCirc and D-Flow FM follow the exact time history closely all along. The Telemac results show narrowing oscillations of water level and depth-averaged velocity as well as time lagging. While triaging errors is beyond scope here, such a flaw might reside in specifics activated by the linearisation and/or in algorithms that serve the more general formulation of the shallow-water equations.

Figure 2: Computed versus exact time histories for three solvers. Frictionless basin, $\lambda = 0$. — Left: water level at the downwind end. Right: velocity at the open boundary. — Exact time history shown in Figure 1

Verification tests also address questions of usage (presented at the symposium). For example, the size of the mesh elements sets the smallest wavelengths in equation (2) that a solver can calculate. In turn, equation (4) indicates which period pertains to these shortest waves that can live on the mesh. Hence, for a truly complete numerical solution, the time step should not exceed the half of this period — here, $\Delta t_{max} = 5.78$ s. The loss of accuracy incurred when larger time steps are used, for example with the aim of reducing the simulation time, is then quantified referring to the exact solutions.

3. Conclusions

Computer simulations are instrumental in supporting societal decisions on the management of flood-prone areas, in the first place by contributing to the quantification of both dimensions of risk: hazard and damage. Different numerical solvers simulating the same flow are expected to produce the same results, theoretically. However, the stages of formulation, discretisation, numerical integration and coding of a flow solver may introduce inaccuracies other than flavours.

Conveniently, linearised governing equations describe key aspects of the mechanics at play in storm surges that remain relevant with a more complex dynamics. Hence, their exact solutions provide a means to verify the performance of the flow solvers. While no single verification exercise is exhaustive, each enables developers and users to identify and triage areas of caution and improvement.

Leaning on the work of Sobey (2002) and taking advantage of several flow solvers being open-source software, this contribution opens a view on assumptions, scope and applications of a unified assessment of storm-surge simulations.

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